

weeds and recorded least weed dry matter and maximum WUE, followed by 2 hand weedings (HW) (15 and 30 d after transplanting [DT]) both seasons.

The combined approach of irrigation to 5-cm submergence 1 d after water disappeared and weed control through preemergence butachlor plus

postemergence 2,4-D sodium salt could save irrigation water in transplanted rice that otherwise would be used by competing weeds. □

Managing other pests

A crab trap for a deepwater rice (DWR) pest

D. N. Das, B. Roy, and P. K. Mukhopadhyay, Deepwater Rice Pest Management Project (IRRI/ICAR/Government of West Bengal Cooperative Project), Rice Research Station (RRS), Chinsurah, West Bengal 712102, India

In West Bengal, common freshwater crabs *Paratelphusa hydrodromus* Herbertson and *P. spinigeru* Wood-Manson (Family Potamidae) damage DWR by cutting elongating stems. Damage is most severe in fish - rice culture. Chemical methods, including bleaching powder (calcium chloro hypochlorite), fail to control them.

We designed a crab trap of fine bamboo sticks bound with nylon thread

(see figure). Smooth entry points let crabs in, bamboo sticks projecting inside the box keep them from leaving. DWR farmers use similar devices to trap wild fish and prawns in their fields. We tested

the crab traps in 1987 wet season. Traps were baited with snail-meat and left in the water overnight. Each trap collected 30-40 crabs/d during Aug-Sep. The crabs can be eaten. □

Device used to trap field crabs in Chinsurah, West Bengal, India, 1987 kharif.

Farming systems

Performance of rice-based cropping systems in river floodplains

S. B. Singh and R. D. S. Yadav, N.D. University of Agriculture and Technology, Crop Research Station, Masodha, Faizabad 224001, India

We evaluated seven rice-based cropping systems for Gomti river floodplain in 1983-84. Soil had 0.20% organic C, 6.2 kg P, and 119 kg K with pH value of 7.7. Rice (*Oryza sativa*) variety Saket 4 was directly seeded in rows 20 cm apart in 6- × 5-m plots. After harvesting the wet season rice crop, wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), barley (*Hordeum vulgare*),

Rice yield equivalent and net profit of rice-based cropping systems in Gomti River floodplain. Faizabad, India.

Cropping system	Grain yield (t/ha)		Total yield (t/ha)	Total yield equivalent (t/ha)	Net profit (\$/ha)
	Wet season	Dry season			
Rice - wheat (C-306)	1.31	1.96	3.27	3.50	216.72
Rice - barley (Azad)	1.24	2.11	3.35	3.33	212.88
Rice - chickpea (Radhey)	1.21	0.11	1.32	1.40	32.16
Rice - lentil (T36)	1.24	0.41	1.65	2.06	124.00
Rice - safflower (T45)	1.22	0.34	1.59	1.77	88.64
Rice - taramira (T-136)	1.33	0.29	1.62	2.02	36.00
Rice - mustard (Varuna)	1.31	0.59	1.90	3.46	223.28

chickpea (*Cicer arietinum*), lentil (*Lens esculenta*), safflower (*Carthamus tinctorius*), taramira (*Eureca sativa*), and mustard (*Brassica juncea*) were sown during dry season (DS). The experiment was in a randomized block design with four replications. Grain yields of DS crops were converted to rice yield

equivalents and net profits computed (see table).

Rice yield equivalents of rice - wheat and rice - mustard crops were highest, with rice - barley next. Rice - chickpea produced least. Rice - mustard gave net profit of \$223.28/ha, followed by rice - wheat with \$216.72/ha.